

EFFECT OF ABSORBED POWER AND TEMPERATURE NON-UNIFORMITY ON THE RAPID MICROWAVE SINTERING OF VARISTOR CERAMICS

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This paper reports the results of a study of microwave sintering of ZnO-based varistor ceramics in rapid processing regimes. The study has established correlation of enhanced densification with the development of thermal instability at elevated levels of the absorbed microwave power density. Based on an analysis of the experimental data, a mechanism underlying rapid densification in different field-assisted processes with volumetric energy release is discussed.

The samples for the study were compacted from a ZnO + 1.5 mol. % Bi₂O₃ + 1 mol. % Sb₂O₃ powder mixture with an average particle size of 0.5 – 1 μm. The samples were pressed uniaxially into pellets 10 mm in diameter and about 3 mm in thickness. The density of the compacted samples was about 55 % of the theoretical value. Microwave sintering was carried out on a 24 GHz / 5 kW gyrotron system for high-temperature processing of materials [1]. The gyrotron output power was regulated continuously by the computer control system to implement the specified heating regimes. After an initial slow heating needed to remove the adsorbed water, starting from a temperature of 500 °C the samples were heated at a constant heating rate, 10 – 130 °C/min, up to a temperature of 1100 – 1300 °C with no isothermal hold. The temperature of the samples was measured by two type B thermocouples, one installed in a hole drilled to the center of the sample and the other touching the surface of the sample at a distance of 1 mm from its edge. The reading of the former thermocouple was used as a driving signal for the power control system. The thermal insulation assembly comprised a block of porous alumina (AL-30, Zircar Ceramics, USA) with an 11 mm dia. cylindrical channel drilled through it to make the sample visible for the optical dilatometry unit [2]. In some experiments, a SiC susceptor ring was built in the assembly around the sample to improve the temperature uniformity. Higher heating rate experiments (75 – 130 °C/min) were carried out using a closed thermal insulation assembly without the use of optical dilatometry. For purposes of comparison, some samples were sintered conventionally in a resistive furnace with a heating rate of 3 °C/min and an isothermal hold for 30 min.

The relative densities of the sintered samples and the mass loss are plotted in Fig. 1 for different maximum sintering temperatures as a function of the heating rate. It can be seen that under direct microwave sintering the highest final densities, about 96 % of the theoretical value, were achieved at a maximum sintering temperature of 1150 – 1200 °C using rather high heating rates: 50 and 75 °C/min. Using a SiC susceptor, a similar density was achieved at a heating rate of 30 °C/min. The mass loss of the samples increased when the heating rate was below 50 °C/min or when the maximum sintering temperature was raised to 1300 °C. The conventionally sintered samples exhibited a one percentage point lower density and a twofold increase in the mass loss compared to the samples sintered in the optimal microwave processing regimes.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. The final density of the sintered samples (a) and the mass loss (b) for different final sintering temperatures vs. the heating rate.

Examples of SEM images of the samples obtained by microwave and conventional sintering are shown in Fig. 2. The average grain size determined using the method of

random sections was 3.7 – 4.3 μm in the samples microwave sintered at 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 5.1 μm in the samples microwave sintered at 1300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and 5.8 μm in the samples sintered conventionally at 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with an isothermal hold for 30 min.

Fig. 2. SEM images of the of the polished and etched surfaces of the samples obtained by (a) microwave sintering (50 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, no hold); (b) conventional sintering (3 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 30 min hold).

The current–voltage characteristics obtained for some of the obtained varistor ceramic samples are shown in Fig. 3. The nonlinearity index determined for all samples falls within the range 32 – 35. The breakdown electric field strength is approximately inversely proportional to the average grain size.

Fig. 3. Current – voltage characteristics of the samples of varistor ceramics sintered at a temperature of 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ by microwave sintering at different heating rates and by conventional sintering (two samples).

An investigation of the rapid microwave sintering mechanism responsible for the densification in the described experiments involves an analysis of the shrinkage data, the automatically regulated microwave power recorded during the constant-heating-rate processes, and the temperature difference between the center and periphery of the samples. Shown in Fig. 4 are the dependencies of the relative density on the temperature measured in the center of the samples obtained by optical dilatometry. It can be seen that the densification in the process using the SiC susceptor ring starts at a temperature of about 750 °C which is noticeably higher than in all other samples.

Fig. 4. The relative density of the samples during microwave sintering vs. the temperature of the center of the samples, including a process carried out with a SiC susceptor ring.

Shown in Fig. 5 are the plots of the automatically regulated microwave power recorded in the microwave sintering processes carried out at the same heating rate, 30 °C/min, with and without the SiC susceptor. Small temperature and power oscillations seen in the plots reflect the operation of the automatic power control algorithm. It can be seen that when the susceptor is utilized, the recorded power grows monotonically with temperature, remaining significantly lower throughout the process than the power recorded in the case of direct microwave heating without using the susceptor. The relatively low power required for heating in the former case is explained by strong microwave absorption in SiC. In the latter case a transient drop in the power is observed in the temperature range 650 – 750 °C. The power decreases to the values that are close to the power recorded in the process utilizing the susceptor. This suggests that in this temperature interval there develops a strong microwave absorption in the material of the sample. Comparing the respective curves in Figs. 4 and 5, one can conclude that this strong microwave absorption coincides with the onset of densification in the sample. A similar transient decrease of the automatically regulated power was observed in the same temperature range in all microwave heating processes carried out without the susceptor at different heating rates [3].

Fig. 5. The automatically regulated microwave power recorded in the microwave sintering processes carried out at a constant heating rate of 30 °C/min with and without the use of a SiC susceptor vs. the temperature of the center of the samples.

In situ measurements of the dc electric conductivity of the varistor ceramic samples during microwave heating have demonstrated that the conductivity begins to increase sharply at a temperature of about 700 °C. It should be noted that liquid phase begins to form in the ZnO – Bi₂O₃ system at about 735 °C [4], and in the presence of Sb₂O₃ this temperature can decrease to as low as ~ 590 °C [5]. The liquid phase has orders-of-magnitude higher electric conductivity than the solid ceramic composition, and it contributes significantly into both the dc conductivity and the microwave absorption. The drop in the microwave power seen in Fig. 5 results from the reaction of the power control system on the increase in the temperature of the sample center in excess of the preset temperature-time schedule. This temperature increase is a manifestation of the thermal instability that develops when the volumetrically released microwave power, increasing due to the growing absorption, is no more balanced by heat removal. Such instability has been detected in the previous studies of rapid microwave sintering of other ceramic materials [2, 6–8]. The liquid phase forming at the powder particle surfaces enhances the mass transport rates in the sintering process drastically. This explains the early onset of densification seen in Fig. 4. In contrast, when the SiC susceptor is utilized, a significant portion of the microwave power is absorbed in it, and the sample undergoes hybrid heating resulting from both microwave absorption in the sample and the heat flow from the susceptor. This prevents the development of the instability because the power absorbed volumetrically in the sample does not reach the threshold value at which the heat balance is violated. As demonstrated in [3], the temperature difference between the center and the periphery of the sample at a heating rate of 30 °C/min is reduced by an order of magnitude, from 200 °C in the case of direct microwave heating to about ± 20 °C in the case of utilizing the susceptor.

As can be seen from Fig. 4, the onset of densification and the maximum of the densification rate are shifted by about 80 – 100 °C towards lower temperatures in the case of direct microwave heating. A possible reason for this is the thermal stress arising in the non-uniform temperature field, which can provide an additional driving force for densification [9].

In conclusion, samples of ZnO + Bi₂O₃ + Sb₂O₃ varistor ceramics have been sintered to 95 – 96 % of the theoretical density in rapid microwave heating processes with no isothermal hold. The elevated microwave heating rates make it possible to restrict the grain growth and limit the mass losses of the samples. The total duration of the high-temperature sintering stage is reduced by more than an order of magnitude compared to the conventional sintering process. The controlled thermal instability arising in the samples enhances the densification due to early liquid phase formation. High density of the volumetrically absorbed microwave power causes significant temperature gradients and appreciable thermal stresses in the sample. Finally, it can be argued that the described mechanism of rapid densification associated with the development of thermal instability and formation of liquid or softened phases at particle surfaces is applicable to different field-assisted sintering processes involving volumetric heat deposition, including flash sintering.

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References

- [1] Bykov, Yu.V., A.G. Ereemeev, M.Yu. Glyavin, G.G. Denisov, G.I. Kalynova, E.A. Kopelovich, A.G. Luchinin, I.V. Plotnikov, M.D. Proyavin, M.M. Troitskiy, V.V. Kholoptsev, *Radiophys. Quantum Electron.*, 2019, **61**, 752–762, DOI 10.1007/s11141-019-09933-6
- [2] Egorov, S.V., A.G. Ereemeev, V.V. Kholoptsev, I.V. Plotnikov, K.I. Rybakov, A.A. Sorokin, Yu.V. Bykov, *Scripta Mater.*, 2020, **174**, 68–71, DOI 10.1016/j.scriptamat.2019.08.032
- [3] Egorov, S.V., A.G. Ereemeev, V.V. Kholoptsev, I.V. Plotnikov, K.I. Rybakov, A.A. Sorokin, S.S. Balabanov, E.Ye. Rostokina, Yu.V. Bykov, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 2021, DOI 10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2021.06.028
- [4] Clarke, D.R., *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1999, **82**, 485–502, DOI 10.1111/j.1151-2916.1999.tb01793.x
- [5] Arefin, M.L., F. Raether, D. Dolejs, A. Klimera, *Ceram. Int.*, 2009, **35**, 3313–3320, DOI 10.1016/j.ceramint.2009.05.030
- [6] Bykov, Yu.V., S.V. Egorov, A.G. Ereemeev, V.V. Kholoptsev, K.I. Rybakov, A.A. Sorokin, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 2015, **98**, 3518–3524, DOI 10.1111/jace.13809
- [7] Bykov, Yu.V., S.V. Egorov, A.G. Ereemeev, V.V. Kholoptsev, I.V. Plotnikov, K.I. Rybakov, A.A. Sorokin, *Materials*, 2016, **9**, 684, DOI 10.3390/ma9080684
- [8] Bykov, Yu.V., S.V. Egorov, A.G. Ereemeev, V.V. Kholoptsev, I.V. Plotnikov, K.I. Rybakov, A.A. Sorokin, S.S. Balabanov, A.V. Belyaev, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 2019, **102**, 559–568, DOI 10.1111/jace.15788
- [9] Rybakov, K.I., V.E. Semenov, *Philos. Mag. A*, 1996, **73**, 295–307, DOI 10.1080/01418619608244384